

TRANSLATION WAYS OF BORROWINGS

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Abstract. One of the difficulties in the translation process is the translation of borrowings due to the lack of equivalent concepts and expressions in one language's vocabulary. Therefore, this study aimed to discuss several translation methods of borrowings. Three main translation ways of borrowings have been analyzed, including, transcription, transliteration, calque and descriptive translation. Each translation method is backed up with examples. Selecting the right approach is a crucial step in transferring the meaning of the source language vocabulary to the receptor language.

Keywords: borrowings, translation methods, transcription, transliteration, calque, descriptive translation.

Introduction. Translation is the process of transferring the meaning from the source language to the target language. Newmark claimed that the translation is rendering the meaning of ST into TT. According to Nida translation is reproducing a natural equivalent in the receptor language. In the translation process because of equivalent lacking words translation problems can occur. Mona Baker stated that “non-equivalence at word level means that the target language has no direct equivalent for a word which occurs in the source text”. Words that lack equivalents include terms that are specific to a culture, new concepts, dialect words, slang, taboo words, foreign terms, proper names, misspellings, archaisms, etc. Words taken from other languages in order to describe things, processes, and behaviors that have no equivalent words or expressions in one's native tongues are known as linguistic borrowings. When translating borrowed words into target language, certain translation strategies must be applied.

Methods. When it is determined that the target audience is unfamiliar with the source language's expression, different translation techniques should be applied to address different types of borrowings.

Results and analysis.

The main ways of translation:

- Transliteration and transcription
- Loan translation - calque
- Descriptive translation

Transliteration and transcription are two methods for translating words and phrases that have no alternative variant. They are borrowed from target language according to the orthography and pronunciation of source language.

Transliteration is the method of copying the letters of the source language by the target language letters of another system: Sanskrit: योग: (yoga) – uzbek: yoga, japanese: カラオケ (Karaoke) – uzbek: karaoke, English: credit – uzbek: kredit.

Transliteration is the process of transforming letters into another alphabet. Every character in the source language is assigned to a distinct character in the target language.

Some problems have arisen in transliterating source language letters to target language: i.e. champagne, brigade, circus because all of the languages alphabets and sounds do not coincide. That is why transcription method is used to overcome this issue.

Transcription is the method of copying the sound form of the source language word by means of the target language letters. There are particular guidelines for representing English sounds by Russian letters or English sounds by Uzbek letters.

A transcription is the conversion of the characters of one language to the characters of another language in accordance with the pronunciation of the target language: dealer-diler, management-menejment, agency-agentlik, balcony- balkon.

Transliteration, defined as “to represent or spell in the characters of another alphabet,” or transcription, defined as “to represent (speech sounds) by means of phonetic symbols.” The former aims to represent terms’ standard spelling, or orthography, while the latter aims to represent terms’ standard pronunciation, or phonology. For some languages, a single transliteration system can simultaneously serve both orthographic and phonetic needs because orthography reasonably approximates the pronunciation. Uzbek is one example of a language that is easily represented in orthographic transliteration in Latin script, which allows a foreign reader without specific training or experience to speak and remember the language with ease. On the other hand, because of the significant differences in spelling and

pronunciation, English requires for two different schemes: transliteration and transcription.

Mostly geographical names, proper names and terms are transliterated or transcribed when a target language lacks a certain notion and borrows it a short foreign form. According to Proshina many international loan terms are Greek or Latin origin. This facilitates mutual understanding among specialists: Tragoedia - tragediya, hematoma — gematoma.

Words that are borrowed, without altering their form or meaning, from one language to another are known as **loan words or calques**. Using loanwords or calques is another method for translating words and phrases that have no exact counterpart.

According to Wikipedia, in linguistics, a calque or loan translation is a word or phrase borrowed from another language by literal word-for-word or root-for-root translation. When used as a verb “to calque” means to borrow a word or phrase from another language while translating its components, so as to create a new lexeme in the target language: viral infection – virusli infeksiya, mass culture- ommaviy madaniyat, honeymoon- asal oyi, point of view- nuqtai nazar, labour contract- mehnat shartnomasi, AIDS (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome)- OITS (Orttirilgan Immunitet Tanqisligi Sindromi)

There can occur half-calques in cases where half of the word is borrowed through transcription or transliteration and the other half is translated: online education – onlayn ta’lim, micro economy- mikro iqtisodiyot

Calque translation can be very tricky as it may result in “translator’s false friends”, i.e. misleading translations:

- high school – o’rta maktab (not yuqori maktab)
- restroom – xojatxona (not dam olish xonasi)

Another method for translating terms and expressions that have no exact equivalent is to utilize **descriptive translation**. It is a way of revealing the source lexicon by using phrases or sentence in target language to define its meaning. Instead of direct borrowing, words are translated by using several words to explain the meaning of the target language vocabulary. This technique is used for verbalizing new objects, lexemes not existing in the target language, for example, showmanship- e’tiborni jalb qilish mahorati, journeyman- yollanma ishlaydigan malakali ishchi yoki hunarmand.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the translation of words which has no equivalent form in another language can be really challenging process in translation. There are several methods for translating borrowings which are taken from other languages. Translation and transcription, calques, descriptive translation are the main strategies for conveying the meaning of source language's non-equivalent vocabulary to the target language. In the explanation of the new notion choosing an appropriate method is really essential aspect.

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